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Thyroid Hormone Dysregulation Potential of Gas Flare Exposure

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ABSTRACT

The impact of long term exposure to gas flare on thyroid hormones of women (pregnant and non-pregnant), living in two communities (Bonny and Omoku) in the Niger Delta Regions of Nigeria was conducted, with Idah, Kogi State as control. Blood samples were collected from volunteers. The plasma was extracted after centrifugation and analysed. The thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH), triiodothyronine (T₃) and thyroxine (T₄) were tested. All analyses were done using standard analytical methods. Results for all parameters tested, TSH (mIU/mL), T₃ (ng/mL), and T₄ (nmol/L) were all within the reference ranges. The highest recorded value for TSH (mIU/mL) was 1.55±0.15 and the lowest was 1.92±0.14, both of which were recorded for non-pregnant and pregnant women of Omoku respectively. The highest recorded value for T₃ (ng/mL) was 1.27±0.07 recorded for non-pregnant women of Kogi and the lowest was 1.30±0.07 recorded for pregnant women of Omoku. The lowest value for T₄ was 90.21±1.54, and the highest was 120.93±4.89, both recorded for non-pregnant and pregnant women of Bonny respectively. The recorded values for T₄ for non-pregnant women from Bonny was statistically significantly lower than the recorded values for the pregnant women from the Bonny. Also, the recorded values for T₄ for non-pregnant women from Omoku was statistically significantly lower ($p \leq 0.05$) than the recorded values for the pregnant women from Omoku. Though the results did not follow a consistent pattern, the values recorded for samples from the control site, were generally lower than those from the test site. The study thus indicates that exposure to gas flare may have impacted on the thyroid hormones of inhabitants of the gas flare host communities.

Keywords: Gas Flaring, Thyroid Stimulating Hormone, Triiodothyronine, Thyroxine

INTRODUCTION

Oil exploration in Nigeria commenced in 1956 when oil was found in commercial quantities at Oloibiri in the Niger Delta region by Shell Darcy. Profits from the petroleum sector in the country expanded in 1960 and soared during the oil boom of the early 1970s. (Ahmadu and Egbodion, 2013; Mokelu *et. al* 2020). After the discovery of crude oil in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria and the subsequent initiation of gas flaring, flaring operations have gradually intensified in the area. Around 17.2 billion cubic meters of natural gas are burned off annually in Nigeria, particularly within the Niger Delta region. (GGFRI, 2000). Air, land, and water pollution from gas flaring, frequent oil blowouts, and spills are common occurrences in the region. (Njeze, 1983; Adienbo, and Nwafor, (2010).

Approximately ninety-five percent (95%) of waste gases from the production fields and operation are flared. Gas flaring, though common practice in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria, contributes to pollution of the air with gaseous pollutants which are hazardous to the ozone layer and lead to climate change (IPCC, 2007). It is a major global environmental concern, due to its high emissions of methane, CO₂ and benzene, which are known

ozone-depleting substances and contribute to the global climate change phenomenon (World Bank, 2008; Ndinwa *et al.* 2020). Natural gas, consisting primarily of methane, with varying amounts of other higher alkanes; ethane, propane, butanes, etc. (Ismail and Umukoro, 2012), as well as, oxides of Nitrogen, Carbon and Sulphur, (NO₂, CO₂, CO, SO₂) particulate matter and hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) (Aregbe, 2017), is formed when layers of decomposing plant and animal matter are exposed to intense heat and pressure over thousands of years. Another chief constituent of natural gas is volatile organic compounds (VOCs), a group of organic pollutants, whose wide distribution has attracted considerable attention in environmental science. Benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylenes (o-, m- and p-) (BTEX), are the main representatives of VOCs. They have carcinogenic and mutagenic effects. Exposure to BTEX is associated with adverse effects on the liver, nervous system, heart, kidneys and increases the risk of developing non lymphocytic leukemia (Yu, *et al.*, 2022). The energy that plants originally obtained from the sun is stored in the form of chemical bonds in natural gas. Natural gas is often informally referred to simply as “gas”, especially when compared to other energy sources such as oil or coal (Ismail and Umukoro, 2012; Aregbe, 2017).

The implication of gas flaring on human health are all related to the exposure of those hazardous air pollutants emitted during incomplete combustion of gas flare. Sulfur dioxide (SO₂) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x) released into the atmosphere (Ajugwo, 2013; Pearce & Braverman, 2009), along with thiocyanates, can act as inhibitors of the sodium/iodine symporter (NIS), potentially interfering with thyroid function. Though their effects at environmental exposure levels are not fully understood, they may influence the thyroid hormone receptor, increasing the risk of goiter and hypothyroidism, particularly in vulnerable populations (Ajugwo, 2013; Pearce & Braverman, 2009). Other health effects associated with gas flare exposure include cancers, neurological, reproductive and developmental defects, skin problems lung damage blood deformities etc (Aregbe, 2017).

Maps: A, Map of Nigeria showing the study sites, with a close up map of Kogi State showing the control site. B, Map of Rivers state showing the test locations

The study sites, Bonny and Omoku, are located in Rivers State, the very center of Nigeria's Niger Delta region. Bonny is situated around 40 kilometers southeast of Port Harcourt, on the outer southern edge of the Niger Delta formation. This trapezoidal landmass has the following coordinates: Northwest at Latitude 4°33'N and Longitude 7°08'E; Northeast at Latitude 4°30'N and Longitude 7°20'E; Southwest at Latitude 4°22'N and Longitude 7°20'E; and Southeast at Latitude 4°22'N and Longitude 7°08'E. Bonny Island spans an area of approximately 645.6 square kilometers. (Wikipedia), with a network of creeks and waterways right to its center. The region produces a type of crude oil known as Bonny Light oil. A good portion of the crude extracted onshore in Rivers State is transported to Bonny for export. Bonny hosts a handful of oil and gas companies which includes; Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas (NLNG), Mobile oil and gas facility, Shell petroleum etc. (Jumbo and Ihuah 2024). Bonny Island and its neighboring areas have been condemned by various environmental experts from Nigeria, the UK, the USA, and beyond, as some of the most contaminated locations worldwide. A major cause of this environmental degradation has been identified as the ongoing release of associated gases during petroleum extraction (Odo *et. al.* 2019). Omoku, the second test site is situated on latitude 4° 51' 29.16" N longitude 6° 55' 15.24" E (Oweisana, *et. al.*, 2021) and is the headquarters of Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area (Ndoni National Association, 2023), one of the major cities of the Ogba people (African Books Collective, 2023) of Rivers State, Nigeria. The Oil and Gas companies that operate in Omoku are Shell Petroleum Development Company, Total Exploration & Production Nigeria, and Nigerian Agip Oil Company (SPDC, 2023; Wikipedia Free Encyclopedia). The control site, Idah, on the other hand, is situate in the south – west of Kogi state on longitude 5°45' East and latitude 7°5' North. It is bordered to the north and west by Igalamela/Odolu local government, the south by Ibaji local government and the west by Agenebode in Edo state across the River Niger, with a population of 64,320 individuals, and spans 956.11 hectares. Economic pursuits in Idah range from basic to advanced sectors. Agriculture and fishing are prominent due to the area's closeness to the River Niger. Moreover, there are several small-scale industries such as bakeries, palm oil processing, block production, sachet water packaging, and soap production. However, industrial growth is stunted, with the state's sole sanitary ware factory now inactive. (Tokula, A. E., 2019).

The test sites for this research have been plagued with gas flaring and its associated environmental degenerations and destructions for over twenty years. This study was aimed at investigating the possible effects on Thyroid Hormones resulting from the chronic exposure of the inhabitants to this environmental pollution.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection:

Human sampling was done using convenience sampling method. The inclusion criteria were women between the ages of 18 and 54, willing participants who had resided permanently in the host communities for 10 years or more and visited the local health centers during the period the research was conducted. The sample size was 180, and constituted of 60 women from each study location, 30 out of which were pregnant and the other 30 non-pregnant.

Air particulates were collected using active sampling method, with the Air volume sampler Mini Volume Tactical Air Sampler (TAS). The filter papers were extracted after the exercise stored in air tight petri dishes and subsequently transported to the laboratory for analysis. PAHs and Btex were analysed using Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry (GC–MS). The criteria air pollutants were determined using real time monitoring, using the aeroqual series 500 while attaching the relevant sensors for detecting of specific gases. Results are shown in tables 1, 2, and 3 below.

Consent forms and questionnaires were administered to volunteers, after which blood samples were collected. 3mls of blood was collected per volunteer and transported to the lab for laboratory analysis. In the laboratory, the samples were centrifuged and subsequently imputed into the COBAS C III for thyroid hormones analyses. Results obtained are displayed in table 4 below.

RESULTS

Table 1. Criteria Pollutants Analysis for the study sites [Bonny (Test 1), Omoku (Test 2) and Kogi (Control site)]. Results are presented as mean ± Standard Error Mean (S.E.M).

PARAMETERS	KOGI	BONNY	OMOKU	PERMISSIBLE LIMIT
PM _{2.5} µg	0.01±0.0 ^a	0.01±0.00 ^{a,c}	0.02±0.00 ^{a,c}	
PM ₁₀ µg	0.08±0.03 ^a	0.06±0.03 ^{a,c}	0.07±0.02 ^{a,c}	
CO ₂ ppm	769.89±6.04 ^a	63.11±1.61 ^{b,c}	647.44±48.60 ^{b,d}	
CO ppm	0.81±0.47 ^a	2.81±1.73 ^{a,c}	0.00±0.00 ^{a,c}	100 mg/m ³ (90 ppm) for 15 minutes (WHO, 2000)
SO ₂ ppm	0.16±0.10 ^a	0.00±0.00 ^{a,c}	0.00±0.00 ^{a,c}	
NO ₂ ppm	0.07±0.00 ^a	0.07±0.00 ^{a,c}	0.07±0.00 ^{a,c}	0.5 – 1.0 ppm (WHO, 1963)
VOC ppm	0.13±0.09 ^a	0.51±0.29 ^{a,c}	0.10±0.07 ^{a,c}	
CH ₄ ppm	76.89±30.79 ^a	0.00±0.00 ^{b,c}	20.22±4.25 ^{a,c}	
NH ₃ ppm	0.21±0.13 ^a	0.01±0.01 ^{a,c}	0.08±0.08 ^{a,c}	
H ₂ S ppm	0.00±0.00 ^a	0.01±0.01 ^{a,c}	0.00±0.00 ^{a,c}	0.1 – 0.2ppm (WHO,1963)
O ₃ ppm	0.00±0.00 ^a	0.00±0.00 ^{a,c}	0.15±0.01 ^{a,c}	
RH %RH	63.12±3.05 ^a	70.80±1.33 ^{a,c}	46.41±3.37 ^{b,d}	
WS m/s	0.97±0.31 ^a	9.78±7.14 ^{a,c}	0.78±0.19 ^{a,c}	
Temp °C	33.82±1.28 ^a	30.90±0.65 ^{a,c}	37.16±1.32 ^{a,d}	
Noise dB	56.50±2.50 ^a	52.69±2.44 ^{a,c}	62.20±2.53 ^{a,d}	

Values are mean ± Standard Error Mean (S.E.M.). Values with different superscript in the same row are significantly different at the 0.05 levels (p≤0.05). Superscript (a,b) compares Bonny and Omoku to Kogi (1st letters) while superscript (c,d) compares Omoku to Bonny (2nd letters) across the row. PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ are measured in micrograms (µg), CO₂, CO, SO₂, NO₂, VOC, CH₄, NH₃, H₂S, and O₃ were measured in parts per million (ppm), RH, WS, Temp, and Noise were measured in %, m/s, °C and dB respectively.

Table 2. Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon (PAHs) for study sites [Bonny (Test 1), Omoku (Test 2) and Kogi (Control site)]. Results are presented as mean ± Standard Error Mean (S.E.M).

POLYCYCLIC AROMATIC HYDROCARBONS (ppm)	KOGI	BONNY	OMOKU	PERMISSIBLE LIMITS (No safe levels))
Naphthalene	203.86±25.40 ^a	151.34±7.90 ^{a,c}	133.66±11.84 ^{b,c}	
Acenaphthylene	124.71±32.69 ^a	213.58±5.10 ^{b,c}	242.21±4.29 ^{b,c}	
Acenaphthene	163.92±28.00 ^a	167.56±27.89 ^{a,c}	133.47±2.21 ^{a,c}	
Flourene	0.00±0.00 ^a	0.00±0.00 ^{a,c}	38.87±19.44 ^{a,c}	
Phenanthrene	219.88±37.98 ^a	166.70±28.85 ^{a,c}	318.30±12.51 ^{a,d}	
Anthracene	41±31.02 ^a	149.68±45.17 ^{a,c}	104.05±52.03 ^{a,c}	
Flouranthene	115.42±29.15 ^a	90.72±23.88 ^{a,c}	108.13±29.99 ^{a,c}	
Pyrene	71.06±35.53 ^a	97.60±27.06 ^{a,c}	180.63±11.24 ^{b,c}	
Benz(a)anthracene	44.07±22.04 ^a	126.48±32.90 ^{a,c}	108.47±27.15 ^{a,c}	
Chrysene	168.94±47.28 ^a	143.55±42.73 ^{a,c}	187.44±29.89 ^{a,c}	
Benzo(b)flouranthene	0.00±0.00 ^a	0.00±0.00 ^{a,c}	0.00±0.00 ^{a,c}	
Benzo(k)flouranthene	0.00±0.00 ^a	0.00±0.00 ^{a,c}	0.00±0.00 ^{a,c}	

Benzo(a)pyrene	0.00±0.00 ^a	53.07±26.54 ^{a,c}	0.00±0.00
Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene	0.00±0.00 ^a	0.00±0.00 ^{a,c}	0.00±0.00 ^{a,c}
Dibenz(a,h)anthracene	0.00±0.00 ^a	0.00±0.00 ^{a,c}	0.00±0.00 ^{a,c}
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	0.00±0.00 ^a	0.00±0.00 ^{a,c}	0.00±0.00 ^{a,c}
Total PAH	1307.27±180.12 ^a	1360.28±159.10 ^{a,c}	1608.18±82.03 ^{a,c}

Values are mean ± Standard Error Mean (S.E.M.). Values with different superscript in the same row are significantly different at the 0.05 levels ($p \leq 0.05$). Superscript (a,b) compares Bonny and Omoku to Kogi (1st letters) while superscript (c,d) compares Omoku to Bonny (2nd letters) across the row. PAHs were measured in parts per million (ppm).

Table 3. Benzene, Toluene, Ethylbenzene and Xylene (BTEX) for study sites [Bonny (Test 1), Omoku (Test 2) and Kogi (Control site)]. Results are presented as mean ± Standard Error Mean (S.E.M).

BTEX (ppm)	KOGI	BONNY	OMOKU	PERMISSIBLE LIMITS
Benzene	9.95±0.80 ^a	4.37±1.29 ^{b,c}	4.81±1.22 ^{b,c}	No safe levels (WHO,2000)
Toluene	1.76±0.88 ^a	2.36±0.92 ^{a,c}	7.45±1.89 ^{b,d}	0.26 mg/m ³ (WHO, 2000)
o-xylene	6.44±1.91 ^a	3.25±0.96 ^{a,c}	2.90±0.98 ^{a,c}	
m-xylene	2.26±0.67 ^a	4.49±1.08 ^{a,c}	6.12±0.91 ^{b,c}	
p-xylene	11.04±0.99 ^a	5.22±1.43 ^{b,c}	5.61±1.50 ^{b,c}	
Ethylbenzene	7.93±2.64 ^a	3.92±1.36 ^{a,c}	4.11±1.18 ^{a,c}	
Total BTEX	39.37±1.38 ^a	23.62±1.00 ^{b,c}	31.00±0.76 ^{b,d}	

Values are mean ± Standard Error Mean (S.E.M.). Values with different superscript in the same row are significantly different at the 0.05 levels ($p \leq 0.05$). Superscript (a,b) compares Bonny and Omoku to Kogi (1st letters) while superscript (c,d) compares Omoku to Bonny (2nd letters) across the row. BTEX were measured in parts per million (ppm)

Table 4. Thyroid hormones [Thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH), Triiodothyronine (T₃) and Thyroxine (T₄)] of blood samples collected from study participants [Pregnant women (PW) and Non-Pregnant women (NPW)] from study sites [Bonny (test site 1), Omoku (test site 2) and Kogi (control site)]. Results are presented as mean ± Standard Error Mean (S.E.M).

STUDY SITE	TSH (mIU/mL)		T ₃ (ng/mL)		T ₄ (nmol/L)	
	NPW	PW	NPW	PW	NPW	PW
Kogi	1.73±0.16 ^{a, .e}	1.84±0.16 ^{a, .e}	1.27±0.07 ^{a, .e}	1.32±0.07 ^{a, .e}	119.60±6.16 ^{a, .e}	111.50±3.33 ^{a, .e}
Bonny	1.74±0.17 ^{a,c,g}	1.57±0.18 ^{a,c,g}	1.35±0.07 ^{a,c,g}	1.31±0.07 ^{a,c,g}	90.21±1.54 ^{a,c,g}	120.93±4.89 ^{a,c,h}
Omoku	1.55±0.15 ^{a,c,i}	1.92±0.14 ^{a,c,i}	1.31±0.07 ^{a,c,i}	1.30±0.07 ^{a,c,i}	95.85±3.50 ^{a,c,i}	118.63±4.43 ^{a,c,j}
Reference Ranges	0.3 – 4.2		0.8 – 2.0		66 – 181	

Values are mean ± Standard Error Mean (S.E.M.). For 1st and 2nd letter comparisons, comparisons are vertical, i.e., values with different superscript in the same column are significantly different at the 0.05 levels ($p \leq 0.05$). Superscript (a,b) compares Pregnant and Non-Pregnant Women of Bonny and Omoku to Pregnant and Non-Pregnant Women of Kogi (1st letters), superscript (c,d) compares Pregnant and Non-Pregnant Women of Omoku to Pregnant and Non-Pregnant Women of Bonny (2nd letters). For 3rd letter comparisons, i.e., e,f; g,h and i,j, comparisons are horizontal (along the rows), and values with different superscript in the same rows are significantly different at the 0.05 levels ($p < 0.05$). Superscript (e,f) compares Pregnant Women of Kogi to Non-Pregnant Women of Kogi, superscript (g,h) compares Pregnant Women of Bonny to Non-Pregnant Women of Bonny, while superscript (i,j) compares Pregnant Women of Omoku to Non-Pregnant Women of Omoku (3rd letters). TSH, T₃ and T₄ were measured in milli – international units per milliliter (mIU/mL), nanograms per milliliter (ng/mL) and nanomol per liter (nmol/L) respectively.

DISCUSSION

The criteria air pollutants result for the control site, (Idah), showed relatively low levels of pollutants across most parameters. Bonny the first test site, exhibited elevated levels of some pollutants, particularly VOCs (0.51 ppm) and CO (2.81 ppm), while Omoku the second test site, displayed varied pollution levels, with notable levels of PM_{2.5} (0.02 µg), CO₂ (647.44 ppm), and O₃ (0.15 ppm). The results from of the Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon analysis revealed that Omoku exhibited the highest total PAH concentration; 1608.18 ppm, indicating significant pollution, especially for compounds like phenanthrene, acenaphthylene, and pyrene. Bonny followed closely with a total PAH concentration of 1360.28 ppm, and notable levels of acenaphthylene and benzo(a)pyrene. Idah, the control site, though exhibited the lowest level of contamination, still showed relatively high levels of naphthalene, anthracene, and phenanthrene with a total PAH of 1307.27 ppm. Omoku and Bonny, exposed to gas flaring, show significant contamination, particularly Omoku, where toluene and m-xylene concentrations suggest strong flaring effects. The control site however is not void of pollution. The study, emphasizes the need for a comprehensive assessment of all potential pollution sources, even in areas selected as controls, to fully understand the environmental impacts of gas flaring especially as the control site, Idah showed high BTEX levels, despite the absence of gas flaring, indicating that other pollution sources potentially from industrial activities or transportation are contributing to environmental contamination. These findings highlight the complexity of isolating gas flaring impacts, as multiple factors influence BTEX concentrations in the environment.

Though thyroid hormones (TSH, T₃ and T₄) levels were within reference ranges with no statistical significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) across all test sites, except for thyroxine (T₄), which was statistically significantly higher ($p \leq 0.05$) for pregnant women from Bonny and Omoku, when compared to non-pregnant women from respective locations, it is notable that these thyroid hormone results were reflective of the evident air quality results from respective study sites, indicating that the results may be linked to environmental factors resulting from gas flaring in these locations. The thyroid hormone levels for volunteers from the control site, Idah were within the normal reference range and showed consistency between Non Pregnant Women and Pregnant Women, which suggests normal thyroid function. Results for volunteers from the test sites, Bonny and Omoku on the other hand, exhibited significant differences in TSH and T₄ levels compared to Idah, particularly in pregnant women. These changes in the hormone levels though within the reference ranges, may be suggestive of a potential thyroid hormone dysregulation.

CONCLUSION

This study presents a clear correlation between environmental pollution from gas flaring and its potential impact on air quality and thyroid hormone levels in local populations. Bonny and Omoku, the two test sites, demonstrated significantly elevated levels of various air pollutants, including VOCs, PAHs, and CO, with Omoku showing the highest total PAH concentrations, indicating severe environmental contamination from gas flaring activities. The control site Idah, on the other hand, exhibited relatively low pollutant levels, but surprisingly, still showed notable concentrations of specific pollutants such as naphthalene and BTEX compounds, suggesting the influence of other industrial or anthropogenic pollution sources.

Although the thyroid hormone levels remained within reference ranges, there were statistical significant differences in thyroxine (T₄) levels among pregnant women from Bonny and Omoku, pointing to a possible link between environmental pollution and thyroid hormone dysregulation. The consistency in hormone levels at the control site reinforces the hypothesis that gas flaring is contributing to these variations in thyroid function in the affected regions.

These findings underscore the complexity of isolating the impacts of gas flaring on environmental and public health, as multiple pollution sources may interact to influence contaminant levels. This study highlights the importance of a holistic approach to environmental risk assessment that considers all potential pollution sources to better understand and mitigate the impacts of gas flaring on human health and the environment.

This results suggest that the exposure to gas flare may have adversely affected the thyroid hormone synthesis and regulation in the women from gas flare host communities compared to the control site. Though the effect is not morbid, at higher concentrations and longer duration of exposure, it may become morbid and may lead to mortality.

DECLARATION

Data Availability Statement: The data used to support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon request.

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Ethical Approval: Ethical approval was obtained from the University of Port Harcourt.

Conflict of Interest: No conflict of interest

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceptualization, AAJ., MOM. and LCC.; methodology, AAJ. and LCC.; validation, AAJ. and MOM.; formal analysis, AAJ.; investigation, AAJ.; resources, AAJ.; data curation, AAJ., MOM. and LCC.; writing—original draft preparation, AAJ.; writing—review and editing, MOM. And LCC.; supervision, MOM. and LCC.; project administration, AAJ.; funding acquisition, LCC. and AAJ. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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